

Guidelines for providing and handling Schema.org metadata in compliance with Europeana

Linked data aggregation in project Europeana Common Culture

(version 0.1)

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1. Introduction

The linked data functional application of the project Europeana Common Culture applies linked data aggregation in Schema.org, and its transformation into EDM for delivery to Europeana.

Currently, Europeana only supports ingestion of metadata in EDM, but experiments with Schema.org metadata about cultural heritage objects have shown that it can provide good quality data capable of fulfilling the requirements of Europeana.

This document aims to provide a general-level of guidance for usage of Schema.org metadata that, after conversion to EDM, will result in metadata that is suitable for aggregation by Europeana. It can be used by providers of Schema.org metadata that will be converted at a later stage into EDM, or the aggregators performing this conversion from Schema.org to EDM.

We present only the essential aspects that Schema.org metadata must fulfil for aggregation into Europeana, which somehow amounts to identifying a "core" of Schema.org elements needed by Europeana. Beyond these aspects, data providers and aggregators are free to explore all the richness of the Schema.org vocabulary for describing their digital cultural objects in detail.

This remainder of this guide is divided into three parts. Subsection 2 presents an overview of the capabilities of Schema.org for representing cultural heritage resources in the context of EDM. The other two subsections present in detail the requirements that Europeana presents to metadata in Schema.org. Subsection 3 presents the Schema.org classes that are converted to EDM classes. Subsection 4 presents the mandatory (groups of) EDM properties how these are converted from Schema.org metadata.

2. Overview of Schema.org for cultural heritage resources

Schema.org covers the data modelling needs of a wide range of domains. Its level of development varies across domains, however. This section provides a description of how it covers the representation of metadata about cultural heritage resources with a focus on the features represented in Europeana's data model.

For cultural heritage objects, Schema.org's vocabulary allows the description of books, maps, visual art, music recordings, and many other kinds of cultural resources.

The most relevant Schema.org classes for Europeana are `schema:CreativeWork` and several of its refining subclasses, which we detail here with their connection to the main modelling constructs of EDM:

- Several types of `schema:CreativeWork`, such as `schema:VisualArtwork`, `schema:Book`, `schema:Painting`, `schema:Sculpture`, and `schema:Product`, can be matched to EDM's Provided Cultural Heritage Object (CHO) `edm:ProvidedCHO`, which represents the object that cultural heritage institutions provide metadata about (and digitized representations of). Each of these subclasses may be used with more specific properties than the ones available for `schema:CreativeWork`, e.g., `schema:artMedium` for `schema:VisualArtwork`.
- The subclass `schema:MediaObject` and its subclasses `schema:ImageObject`, `schema:VideoObject`, `schema:AudioObject` can be matched to `edm:WebResource`, which represents a digital version of the CHO.
- The `schema:Person`, `schema:Place` and `schema:Organization` classes match the semantics of EDM contextual classes `edm:Agent`, `edm:Place` and `foaf:Organization`.

3. Schema.org classes supported for conversion in EDM

The Schema.org to EDM converter built by Common Culture¹ recognizes instances of the following Schema.org classes as instances `edm:ProvidedCHO`:

- `schema:CreativeWork`
- `schema:VisualArtwork`
- `schema:Painting`
- `schema:Book`
- `schema:ImageObject`
- `schema:Newspaper`
- `schema:Periodical`
- `schema:Photograph`
- `schema:CreativeWorkSeries`
- `schema:Sculpture`

After conversion to EDM, the instances of the classes above will lead to the creation of a corresponding instance of another class defined by EDM: `ore:Aggregation`.

The Schema.org to EDM converter also instances of Schema.org classes into instances of `edm:WebResource` and the contextual classes defined by EDM, as follows:

Schema.org class	EDM class
<code>schema:Thing</code>	<code>skos:Concept</code>
<code>schema:Organization</code>	<code>edm:Agent</code>
<code>schema:Person</code>	<code>edm:Agent</code>
<code>schema:Place</code>	<code>edm:Place</code>
<code>schema:PostalAddress</code>	<code>vcard:Address</code>

¹ The Schema.org to EDM converter built by Common Culture is an ongoing work. Its progress can be followed in the Github repository at <https://github.com/netwerk-digitaal-erfgoed/lod-aggregator>.

schema:AudioObject	edm:WebResource
schema:ImageObject	
schema:WebPage	
schema:MediaObject	
-	cc:License

Note that currently, Schema.org does not define a class for licenses, therefore there is no possibility to describe a license with the properties defined by EDM for cc:License.

4. Required Schema.org properties for an EDM conversion valid for Europeana

Europeana's EDM defines mandatory (groups of) properties for edm:ProvidedCHO and ore:Aggregation resources. In order to obtain the properties of EDM required by Europeana, the original Schema.org metadata must contain properties that convey the same meaning as the mandatory EDM properties.

The following tables present an overview of the EDM properties required by Europeana and the corresponding properties that are needed in Schema.org following these requirements, according to the following legend:

✓ = **Mandatory property**

➡Blue = **at least** one of the **blue** properties should be present (and can be used alongside each other)

➤Red = **at least** one of the **red** properties should be present (and can be used alongside each other)

□Green = **at least** one of the **green** properties should be present (and can be used alongside each other)

Properties for edm:ProvidedCHO		
✓	edm:type	this statement is added by the Schema.org converter, based on the subclass of schema:CreativeWork used in the Schema.org record
✓	dc:language (if edm:type = TEXT)	schema:inLanguage
➤	dcterms:spatial	schema:spatial schema:spatialCoverage schema:locationCreated
➤	dcterms:temporal	schema:temporal schema:temporalCoverage
➤	dc:subject	schema:keywords schema:about schema:contentLocation
➡	dc:title	schema:name
➡	dc:description	schema:description schema:artMedium schema:pagination

Properties for ore:Aggregation		
✓	edm:aggregatedCHO	Automatically added by the Schema.org converter
✓	edm:dataProvider	schema:provider
✓	edm:provider	Automatically added by the linked data aggregation infrastructure of the aggregator
✓	edm:rights	schema:license
□	edm:isShownAt	schema:url
□	edm:isShownBy	schema:associatedMedia schema:audio schema:image